

Beyond the Binaries: Analysis of Field Star Variance and Outliers in the MEarth Transit Survey

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1. ABSTRACT

I examined the outlier variable objects in the field stars of the MEarth transit survey data set. I define an outlier as a field star with variance outside three standard deviations of the mean root-mean-square errors associated with its respective magnitude. The MEarth Project collects data from M dwarf stars, creating a survey of these small objects in search of exoplanets. I wrote a Python program which looked through this data set, and of 2149 fields examined, 578081 objects were found, and of those, 1004 had periods of statistical significance, or 0.17%. My program analyzes the root-mean-square residual of a star to determine if it has particularly high variance given its magnitude. Of these outlier stars, I estimated the best-fitting period for the observed flux using phase dispersion minimization (PDM), and phase-folded light curves. I compiled these stars into a list with basic parameters, such as RA, dec, J-, H-, and K-band magnitudes, and their periods, then I further investigated three by using the SIMBAD Astronomical Database to learn and catalogue their properties.

2. INTRODUCTION

With data from Kepler suggesting there are nearly two planets per M dwarf star, the question is no longer if habitable planets outside our solar system exist, but rather: where are they? Analysis of Kepler data by [CITE] suggests M dwarf stars are the most likely candidate, with about 2 planets per star and 0.5 Earth-like planets at a distance from the star where liquid

water can exist (Dressing & Charbonneau 2013). These cooler, slow-burning small stars have a surface temperature of about 3000K (Johnson, 2014), and make up almost 80% of stars in the Milky Way. These Earth-like planets orbiting M dwarf stars are what the MEarth Transit Survey seeks to detect. For each image of an M dwarf taken, though, there are 50 to 500 stars that make up the field of view in the background. It is these background stars which I study here.

The MEarth Survey's data set is unique in its long-term coverage of these stars. For some I have but a few observations, but for many there are hundreds if not thousands taken over hundreds of nights. While the minimum number of observations for outliers found is 14, the maximum 3642. The Northern Hemisphere location has been running since 2008 with our data from 2011 – 2013. For each target star, MEarth has just as many field star observations. Therefore, this large and consistent data lends itself well to statistical analyses and drawing conclusions.

In these variable stars, it is possible to find extrinsic variables that are part of star systems, most commonly eclipsing binaries. These systems might be composed of two stars or a star and planet, or a star and black hole, etc. Because this data subset has not been so carefully studied before, all of these systems would be marked as an outlier star and subject to our further investigation. Similarly, in intrinsic variables, finding regular or irregular pulsating stars or documenting a stellar flare are also possibilities within the data set. These would be interesting not only to better calibrate observations for MEarth target stars, but also in their own right. Typically, fainter stars exhibit more variance in their luminosity due to noise rather than being a variable star. Brighter stars also have a tendency to become oversaturated in observations that are not calibrated to account for their brightness (which MEarth is not,

because its targets are M dwarfs) which leads to high variability when examining observations where the star is and is not saturated. For this reason, I limited my scope to stars between 7 and 14 J-band magnitude, with the average of root-mean-square errors being less than 0.1 across this range.

3. DATA

Using 16 telescopes over two 8-telescope arrays with f/9 40cm Ritchey-Chretien telescopes, mounted at the Fred Lawrence Whipple Observatory in Mount Hopkins, Arizona in the Northern Hemisphere, and at the Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory in the Southern Hemisphere. MEarth North has been in operation since 2008 and MEarth South was set up recently in early 2014. The data I examined from 2011 to 2013. MEarth works as a survey, monitoring thousands of dwarf stars, taking multiple observations of a star over the course of a night. I examined the MEarth North data only, which is inoperable during the monsoon season each year, giving roughly 10 months of continuous observing (the monsoon season shifts each year). MEarth monitors 2180 mid to late M dwarf stars within 33pc with $V - J > 2.3$, $J - K_s > 0.7$, and $J - H > 0.15$, and a cadence of 20 to 30 minutes between observations of targets (Newton et al., 2014). When a star's light fluctuates outside of a threshold value, then the telescope is automatically triggered to stay on it, collecting more data as the star dips or flares, until the flux reaches the star's baseline again. This helps automate the process with which MEarth searches for planets around these target dwarf stars.

In each image MEarth captures, there are between 148 and 690 stars that occupy the background field, with a mean of 296 stars per field. These are useful in calibrating the target

star's luminosity against noise, such as that caused by the Earth's atmosphere, for example. These stars can also be used to make calculations about the target stars themselves, such as determining distance by the parallax. However, with these stars, over the eight telescopes that make up MEarth North, 578081 field stars that have been observed, ranging from 4 observations to 11541 observations, with a mean of 1264. Data was collected from the end of the monsoon season in Arizona to its start, which varies from year to year but the observatory is always closed in August.

Whereas MEarth has created a census for many of its targets stars—there are directly measured distances for 1507 (Dittman, et al. 2014) and metallicities for 447 of the nearby M dwarfs (Newton, et al. 2014)—as well as made rarer discoveries such as a brown dwarf star in a triple system (Irwin, et al. 2010), there is little information concerning just what is in the background of these stars.

4. ANALYSIS

4.1: *Overall Field Variance*

In cases of data prone to large variations, the root mean square often is used to provide a better estimate for it, than the arithmetic mean. From this RMS, its error is defined as the square root of the square of the residual between the predicted value and the actual value. The predicted value in this case is the mean magnitude of the star, and so this is an estimate of how much a star is varying—the equation for root mean square and its error,

$$x_{RMS} = \sqrt{\frac{x_1^2 + x_2^2 + \dots + x_n^2}{n}}$$

$$RMS\ Residuals = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{t=1}^n (\hat{x} - x_t)^2}{n}}$$

For dim stars, smaller aberrations in atmospheric noise on Earth cause greater relative variation than in higher magnitude stars. As seen in Fig 1., where dim stars (those with higher numerical magnitude) are gathered in the top right corner with high RMS fluctuations. Because magnitude is on an exponential scale, the RMS is plotted logarithmically. Brighter stars in this figure, however, are gathered much lower because they have higher flux values so small aberrations from noise and atmosphere make less of a difference. I defined a threshold sigma to determine, of stars with higher variance than expected, which stars are outliers and which are below the threshold and considered noise?

It is not enough to determine this threshold value from the mean RMS of a given field: dim stars will skew the mean, so bright stars will not meet the threshold value while uninteresting dim stars will. Therefore, it is necessary to bin the stars based on their magnitude for these calculations. Again, due to dim stars being so noisy, it behooves us to create a lower limit in the magnitude of stars to examine. There is also an upper limit, though. Many of the very bright stars (magnitude > 6) are likely oversaturated in some images and not in others. As a result, the star has a high RMS without any intrinsic variability. Finally, because magnitude is exponentially increasing, the RMS can be plotted logarithmically to properly show the proportionality between it and magnitude.

Figure 1: Telescope 02 targeting LSPM 2643 showing each field star's J-band magnitude plotted against its RMS (in logarithmic scale).

I wrote in Python follows this algorithm checking each field, and creating a plot of all the field stars. Then the algorithm scans between magnitude 7 and 14 stars with bins equivalent to one magnitude, checking the mean for that magnitude's bin, and finding any stars with RMS above 5 standard deviations of the mean.

Once the program has found those outliers, it is not enough to plot their observed flux against time.

Figure 2: Telescope 1 targeting LSPM3869, due to the time gap and the large block of data, while one can see it varies, it is hard to tell much else

Once the program has found those outliers, it uses phase dispersion minimization (PDM) in order to determine a statistically significant best-fitting period.

4.2 Phase Dispersion Minimization

PDM derives from “folding” the data, essentially by looking at a set of trial periods, it chops the data by those periods and then overlays the different pieces on top of one another in a range of 0 to 1—this range is the “phase.” Then, if there is convergence of the data for a certain period, that is the best-fitting period. To determine this convergence, I first must take the variation over the total data set, utilizing the root mean square—sigma in this case. I define

N to be the number of points in the dataset, and x to be the magnitudes with time t over the i th observation.

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{\sum(x - \bar{x})^2}{N - 1}$$

Where $\bar{x}$ is the arithmetic mean given by $\frac{\sum x_i}{N}$. With each trial-period, I need to determine its variance. For our PDM analysis, the trial periods used were two concatenated arrays: the first being a range starting from 0.01 to 8 in 0.01 increments, and a second logarithmic scale of base 2, with exponents starting at -6 to 5, generating 400 points between this range, for a set of 1199 trial periods. Trial periods required greater accuracy for smaller values that are more susceptible to noise levels (such as between 0.2 and 0.3 days), than larger periods, where there is less relative difference (such as between 15 and 16 days).

Because I wanted to find a converging graph that still displays overall variance, I have to examine the data across different bins, splitting it into smaller pieces. In this case, j is equivalent to the bin number of M bins. Across this trial-period data set, I can essentially treat it as a histogram where each bin is considered a bar and I calculate the standard error bars (s_j) accordingly. In calculating the final error, I only count the points that are outside standard error bars, and n_j is the number of data points within the j th bin. The overall variance of the samples for a trial period is given by

$$s^2 = \frac{\sum(n_j - 1)s_j^2}{\sum n_j - M}$$

Then in order to measure the variance for a specific trial-period, I can create a theta statistic that describes the ratio of the trial-period's variance over the data set's overall variance,

$$\theta = \frac{s^2}{\sigma^2}$$

Because θ is a ratio, it often stays around 1—usually a false period results in no improvement in variance. However, there are cases of particularly ill-fitting periods that actually increase the variance per bin and results in a theta greater than 1. In the case of a well-fitting period, the theta is much lower. In this program, I used 10 bins to calculate the sample period's average variance.

I decided to use a significance threshold in order to quantitatively demonstrate whether a period would be considered well-fitting or not. I chose a sigma of 5 standard deviations outside the mean theta of the trial period set to be that threshold. Stars with significant periods were then considered variable outliers, whereas stars without significant periods were conclude to not have discernible periodic behavior.

While PDM works well for data with high variance, there are still cases where data can have a skewed and non-uniform distribution for no extrinsic reason. There are various cases where noisy data will make PDM finding a significant θ much more difficult. There is a fine line between enough bins to accurately cover a trial-period without the oscillations themselves making the data appear too noisy, and too many bins that can actually increase the relative noise level per bin. The PDM code was written by Harvard astronomer Peter K. G. Williams, and was integrated into my overall code.

4.3 Significance Sampling

To test the significance, I can use the Monte Carlo technique—repeated random samplings to determine a probabilistic result. By randomly generating a data set many times, I can observe if those types of non-uniformity would form in the case of a totally random distribution, or if the null is true and there is no significance in the theta, there will be a comparable theta statistic for the random distribution between the compiled bin variance and the overall variance. By producing random distributions hundreds of times, I invoke the law of large numbers and I reduce the probability of a false-positive to the test. If I take μ to be the true mean of this distribution, where the absolute error $(|\hat{\mu}_n - \mu|)$ will eventually converge to 0 and stay at convergence as the distribution is generated approaching infinity iterations,

$$\mathbb{P}(\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} |\hat{\mu}_n - \mu| = 0) = 1$$

If I assume the distribution has finite variance, that is $Var(X) = \sigma^2 < \infty$, then

$$\mathbb{E}[\hat{\mu}_n] = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbb{E}[X_i] = \mu$$

In an unbiased distribution. The variance is then

$$\mathbb{E}[(\hat{\mu}_n - \mu)^2] = \frac{\sigma^2}{n}$$

Then to calculate the root mean square error of $\hat{\mu}_n$ to better describe this relationships

$$\sqrt{\mathbb{E}[(\hat{\mu}_n - \mu)^2]} = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$$

$$RMSE = O\left(n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\right) \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

The limiting factor in this is $n^{-\frac{1}{2}}$, which means if one wanted to raise the accuracy to one more decimal requires tenth the RMSE and 100 more iterations. Monte Carlo sampling is therefore helpful for a rough significance test. Monte Carlo distributions were run over 256 iterations. It essentially becomes a model of the null hypothesis where I know there is no underlying relationship creating any periodic behavior I observe in the sampling. If I used PDM to find a theta comparable to that of the actual data, then it is unlikely that period has any statistical significance.

4.4. *Phase Folding the Light Curves*

Once I have a period that minimizes variance, I must then actually phase fold the data. First, for all of the observations there is an associated Heliocentric Julian Day that serves as its timestamp. Taking the first HJD of the dataset, I then subtract it from all following times. This results in all data points being associated with a “relative time”. Then, each of these relative HJD times are divided by the best-fitting period; this puts the relative times in units of the best-fitting period. Finally, I took the decimals of these ratios by modulo of the quotient by 1. This is what I plot the flux against for the final light curve.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1 *V728 Cygni*

Figure 3: Telescope 05 targeting LSPM1419 light curve showing Algol-type eclipsing binary

In telescope 05 targeting LSPM1419, I found a best-fitting period of 2.06 days with a theta of 0.18, meaning variance was reduced by 80% giving a much smoother curve than unfolded data. Clearly, there is a significant minimum at 0.2 phases and 1.2 phases, whereas the minima at 0.7 and 1.7 are both nearly 1.0 mag smaller. This means the minima at 0.2 and 1.2 phases are primary, and the others, secondary. In the baselines, the data is not a straight line but has concavity, and in the second phase, there is greater noise than in the first, but a strong pattern is still seen. The distance between the first primary and secondary is nearly equidistant to the first secondary and second primary.

The clear primary and secondary minima indicate that this is possibly a binary star system. The concavity in the baseline is likely due to tidal distortion of their orbit (quite close at 2.06 days) and the equidistance between minima suggests this is a circular orbit, rather than an

elliptical, where the orbiting body has an equal amount of time as it travels along the major axis and goes from in front to behind the planet (and vice versa). The larger primary minima indicate one body is brighter than the second body, and when it is eclipsed there is that larger dip, than when the smaller body is eclipsed the difference in flux is smaller.

Using SIMBAD Astronomical Database, I Were able to use different parameters to look this star up (using J mag, K mag, and H mag). This is V728 Cygni, an Algol eclipsing binary system of A0 spectral type.

5.2 TYC 4254

Figure 4: Telescope 03 targeting LSPM3689 showing sinusoidal variation

In telescope 03 targeting LSPM3689, I find a period of 0.175 with a theta of 0.65. The plot oscillates between 10 mag and 10.35mag, with no primary or secondary minima, but rather a sinusoidal curve. In examining this star in the SIMBAD Astronomical Database, it is indeed a candidate binary system TYC 4254-2686-1. Its entry has a period of 0.35 days, and when plotted against this, a concave-down function was achieved, visually similar to a contact binary system.

Figure 5: Light curve showing a false period

However, because more than one period is seen within one phase, this is instead a false period and does not properly describe the system. Because this period of 0.175 days shows sinusoidal variation, instead of a contact binary system, I believe this to be a pulsating variable star, but would like to do further follow-up to confirm with more observations.

5.3 Odder Outliers

This star fluctuates between nearly 10.7mag and just over 13.2mag. Its period is 1.003days with a theta of 0.35, so despite this wide-banded fit, it reduces variability by half, and the theta distribution's mean is nearly 1. This fit is significant despite its noisy shape. There is no robust, smooth curve, instead the period is just a bit off, creating this widening effect. I can see the plot is mostly concave-up, and there is an odd, nearly backwards-looping curve at the left-most tail. Its crest is nearly at 0.5phase. Increasing the density of period sampling did not change the graph after the significant value of 3. From 0.3phase to 0.5phase, there is a conspicuous hole in data for this graph.

Using the coordinates to search in the SIMBAD Astornomical Database, this is a Seyfert Type II galaxy, 2MASX J00201841+0010310. Theoretically, the program only concerns itself with

field stars, and not background galaxies, but the only stars in the close neighborhood of these coordinates are low mass, and are not known variables. It is unlikely these stars could produce a nearly 2.5mag height between crest and trough. While the Seyfert galaxy could be overshadowing the star and creating odd effects in its light curve, with more precise coordinates, it points directly to the Seyfert galaxy itself. A Seyf

5.5 Tabular Results

See appendix for full table.

6. Conclusion

Over these fields, I now have a better understanding of the visual neighbors near our target stars, both in measuring variance over the entire field and in finding outliers. I have created a program that allows the field stars to be searched based on variance, to find the associated data to these outlier stars, and have determined the identity of a few. While I used fairly high threshold values to determine whether or not a star was considered an outlier, these thresholds can easily be relaxed to find even more varying stars, or increased to find only those with even higher variance. Telescope 1 had the fewest outliers with 82 outliers overall, while Telescope 6 had the highest with 315, with an average of 143 outlier stars for our parameters, per telescope. Of all the fields, there were 1005 outliers, about 0.17% of the field objects. Of these variables, their period was an average of 4.99 days, with an average RMS of about 0.147. In comparison, the first MOTESS-GNAT variable star survey looked over 300deg^2 —for stars between 13 and 19 magnitude, found 26,042 variable star candidates with magnitudes 13 – 19,

and 5271 stars were determined to have periods with 99% confidence (Kraus et al. 2007), or 20%.

While the periods found are statistically significant, this does not necessitate that they are variable stars. While my program picked them out for this significance, the resulting list can be skewed by low frequency of observations, by the trial period set, by instrumentation, etc. In the case of a star with less than 20 observations, 10 bins determining the sample variance may see variance reduced because it is only calculating between two data points. Similarly, while the trial set had 1199 test periods, there are still periods outside this set that might yield better results than the best-fitting period I found. These outside periods might yield a different interpretation, that the star in question is not a variable but some other object. Also, because these stars were not the targets, if their data was collected from the edge of the CCD, pixel sensitivity could affect the measured flux and these results. These are outlier objects, rather than variable star candidates. Therefore, going further with this project, it would be worth sampling even more periods, checking in other surveys for each object, and categorizing whether these are confirmed variables, candidates, or another object entirely. While this study provides descriptions of all the outlier objects, I was unable to look up all of their identities. We now have a better understanding of these background objects, but not an exhaustive inventory.

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Appendix with all results in tabular form:

telescope	lspm	rms	ra	dec	period	min	# of obs	Jmag	Kmag
						theta			
1	lspm1021_lc.fits	0.158698	3.901528	0.204988	0.143229	0.596229	66	14.906	14.5
1	lspm1186_lc.fits	0.054229	4.517455	0.086262	0.185712	0.457819	1048	12.847	12.4
1	lspm1190_lc.fits	0.237387	4.530764	0.201663	2.62	0.668566	2203	14.556	14.1
1	lspm1201_lc.fits	0.038671	4.56901	0.252524	0.757437	0.513398	2342	12.831	12.2
1	lspm1201_lc.fits	0.112917	4.570596	0.252313	0.5	0.134069	2339	14.998	14.0
1	lspm1238_lc.fits	0.193004	4.687419	0.125462	5.21	0.616643	703	13.999	13.6
1	lspm1271_lc.fits	0.107201	4.805508	0.109133	1.99	0.592511	488	10.922	9.6
1	lspm1271_lc.fits	0.050236	4.808037	0.114006	29.19674	0.639456	487	12.618	11.8
1	lspm1301_lc.fits	0.154895	4.912238	0.913383	0.27	0.792882	205	14.965	14.7
1	lspm1364_lc.fits	0.131881	5.152144	0.568965	7.51	0.645382	299	9.07	7.
1	lspm1364_lc.fits	0.084853	5.152413	0.570699	3.944821	0.888422	598	12.068	11.8
1	lspm1395_lc.fits	0.203202	5.250099	0.51998	1.99	0.339812	741	10.771	8.2
1	lspm1395_lc.fits	0.145351	5.247707	0.523683	0.42382	0.943282	1462	11.15	10.8
1	lspm1557_lc.fits	0.119742	5.867811	0.909419	4.00556	0.774743	2798	9.282	7.8
1	lspm1557_lc.fits	0.023244	5.872389	0.909106	1.11	0.28691	2798	10.537	10.2
1	lspm1557_lc.fits	0.050012	5.864706	0.905683	6.26	0.876878	5596	11.654	11.0
1	lspm1557_lc.fits	0.104499	5.866125	0.904001	2.49	0.996295	8385	14.978	14.1
1	lspm1678_lc.fits	0.081854	0.038487	0.861202	0.792966	0.441151	66	12.789	12.5
1	lspm1710_lc.fits	0.029169	0.2687	0.943327	17.36652	0.398741	1633	11.06	10.4
1	lspm1710_lc.fits	0.159957	0.272075	0.9458	0.307487	0.662026	1633	13.522	12.9
1	lspm1710_lc.fits	0.172022	0.273195	0.946386	0.5	0.440547	3266	14.132	13.5
1	lspm1810_lc.fits	0.106239	0.984001	1.272435	3.45	0.500763	142	13.821	13.4
1	lspm1871_lc.fits	0.154716	1.356491	0.327937	15.60491	0.862513	1803	13.507	12.7
1	lspm1885_lc.fits	0.03847	1.523857	0.134615	2.93	0.668368	230	12.886	12.
1	lspm1927_lc.fits	0.083471	1.846238	0.605646	0.097753	0.767691	455	12.661	11.7
1	lspm1947_lc.fits	0.122277	2.012099	0.311594	6.05	0.440384	1409	14.69	13.8
1	lspm2295_lc.fits	0.132379	4.678358	0.65715	0.191475	0.638855	1359	12.415	12.0
1	lspm2301_lc.fits	0.061597	4.73099	1.118064	0.997226	0.306317	596	12.513	11
1	lspm2388_lc.fits	0.112836	5.640782	0.42775	0.478926	0.617901	513	12.547	12.1
1	lspm2463_lc.fits	0.111147	0.026083	1.05479	0.997226	0.447776	546	13.992	13.5
1	lspm2487_lc.fits	0.111413	0.131225	1.356535	0.47	0.808021	2505	12.744	12.2
1	lspm2591_lc.fits	0.20528	0.453816	1.07951	0.997226	0.761555	799	14.708	13.2
1	lspm2617_lc.fits	0.033118	0.543144	1.043066	2.75	0.671138	150	11.786	11.5
1	lspm2683_lc.fits	0.021777	0.806597	1.071274	0.115645	0.572957	111	11.786	11.1
1	lspm2761_lc.fits	0.056343	1.04182	0.663084	3.1	0.663656	128	13.311	12.7
1	lspm2805_lc.fits	0.187096	1.188321	0.829761	3.76	0.313907	200	11.519	10.5
1	lspm2842_lc.fits	0.17927	1.316439	0.397196	4.84	0.639639	88	14.823	14.1
1	lspm28_lc.fits	0.086603	0.088751	0.580083	2.52	0.352434	110	13.575	12.8
1	lspm2931_lc.fits	0.058863	1.756357	1.196923	17.36652	0.606992	226	12.317	11.6
1	lspm2945_lc.fits	0.079945	1.804095	1.093767	1.577144	0.395188	551	13.054	12.
1	lspm2949_lc.fits	0.1925	1.818889	0.38783	1.33	0.627489	123	14.152	13.7

1	lspm2976_lc.fits	0.106075	1.970442	1.401311	0.723501	0.914774	2271	12.694	12.0
1	lspm2978_lc.fits	0.161104	1.956415	0.304759	1.08	0.75173	204	13.937	13.2
1	lspm2978_lc.fits	0.212301	1.956422	0.303744	1.08	0.702543	203	14.592	14.2
1	lspm3032_lc.fits	0.053787	2.186261	0.137113	0.71	0.518891	186	13.047	12.7
1	lspm3674_lc.fits	0.162135	4.735041	0.02616	0.430345	0.224129	312	11.855	11.5
1	lspm3674_lc.fits	0.104253	4.736088	0.025388	0.620983	0.442772	312	13.709	13.3
1	lspm3700_lc.fits	0.05799	4.844273	0.323086	4.5	0.62678	133	12.23	11.8
1	lspm3705_lc.fits	0.877994	4.857996	0.070609	0.997226	0.468954	634	12.812	12.2
1	lspm3731_lc.fits	0.107079	4.922211	0.131381	1.01258	0.543794	523	10.222	8.
1	lspm3731_lc.fits	0.18237	4.923643	0.133891	0.99	0.434535	522	11.231	9.3
1	lspm3760_lc.fits	0.115665	5.026589	0.673783	0.89607	0.678475	1180	13.593	12.9
1	lspm3773_lc.fits	0.029808	5.07685	0.51987	1.04	0.827923	500	11.856	11.0
1	lspm3773_lc.fits	0.11556	5.074941	0.522263	0.997226	0.75803	478	14.665	13.8
1	lspm384_lc.fits	0.103552	1.433051	0.168637	0.110464	0.822398	1078	12.569	11.8
1	lspm3856_lc.fits	0.178819	5.342484	1.294606	0.021868	0.783063	126	13.903	13.2
1	lspm3885_lc.fits	0.052662	5.434146	0.615204	1.51	0.598292	160	11.909	11.0
1	lspm3885_lc.fits	0.188016	5.437046	0.612083	29.64629	0.992027	800	14.884	14.4
1	lspm3892_lc.fits	0.019858	5.449723	0.588284	2.95	0.793414	2030	10.471	9.4
1	lspm3892_lc.fits	0.018968	5.454128	0.583165	1.02	0.846859	2030	11.639	10.4
1	lspm3892_lc.fits	0.054503	5.454931	0.58823	29.64629	0.99644	4067	13.26	12.4
1	lspm3917_lc.fits	0.07448	5.529847	0.963568	1.75	0.647628	194	12.399	11.2
1	lspm3968_lc.fits	0.144911	5.70837	0.788497	0.206677	0.38727	416	13.803	13.3
1	lspm4050_lc.fits	0.112666	6.017287	0.179608	0.436972	0.634371	466	13.889	13.3
1	lspm4067_lc.fits	0.273998	6.072846	1.073083	1.9834	0.396138	863	14.931	13.0
1	lspm4102_lc.fits	0.147368	6.174662	0.672648	0.35825	0.873127	2443	13.819	13.2
2	lspm1299_lc.fits	0.025724	4.90187	0.710368	0.98	0.547086	1362	12.355	11.4
2	lspm1299_lc.fits	0.10548	4.901198	0.709045	30.56625	0.994243	2726	14.432	13.7
2	lspm2337_lc.fits	0.127223	5.060841	0.724874	0.36	0.465982	723	13.551	13.2
2	lspm2980_lc.fits	0.159382	1.970949	0.049207	0.331899	0.377256	1187	14.979	14.
2	lspm3869_lc.fits	0.323074	5.394731	1.115171	1.02	0.652878	728	13.885	10.3
2	lspm3978_lc.fits	0.060631	5.756898	0.09643	10.17314	0.316127	2580	13.98	13.2
2	lspm3924_lc.fits	0.053474	5.525529	1.441136	2.32	0.407189	2201	12.66	11.9
2	lspm1419_lc.fits	0.066535	5.347836	1.025562	0.660121	0.758553	1377	12.977	12.5
2	lspm1419_lc.fits	1.49673	5.343096	1.022441	0.997226	0.398552	1306	13.394	12.9
2	lspm2431_lc.fits	0.081485	6.06899	0.884352	0.64	0.715828	337	11.447	11.0
2	lspm2316_lc.fits	0.052415	4.896427	0.426368	27.04922	0.265754	267	13.217	12.4
2	lspm2316_lc.fits	0.095817	4.895565	0.427105	0.3	0.957765	534	14.416	14.0
2	lspm199_lc.fits	0.156986	0.719899	0.78538	0.174702	0.414453	43	13.758	13.2
2	lspm2298_lc.fits	0.305695	4.698606	0.675435	2.996267	0.915563	537	12.044	11.6
2	lspm1325_lc.fits	0.153887	5.020402	0.306423	2.01	0.599099	182	10.013	8.4
2	lspm1325_lc.fits	0.127036	5.01623	0.304622	2.99	0.312539	71	12.762	11.7
2	lspm1335_lc.fits	0.263997	5.04499	0.091927	0.5	0.444774	777	9.542	7.4
2	lspm1335_lc.fits	0.352443	5.045709	0.089218	1.9834	0.412689	777	10.453	8.8
2	lspm1339_lc.fits	0.062532	5.070265	0.126203	1.01	0.968829	4002	11.046	9.4

2	lspm1370_lc.fits	0.189161	5.177576	0.474212	9.866957	0.432197	979	11.765	10.0
2	lspm1384_lc.fits	0.107113	5.204938	0.771542	2.99	0.350896	64	12.301	11.5
2	lspm1397_lc.fits	0.070842	5.25334	0.102075	3.17	0.608926	471	12.138	11.8
2	lspm1403lspm3833_lc.fits	0.023548	5.261268	0.279653	2.65	0.578492	226	11.503	11.3
2	lspm1403lspm3833_lc.fits	0.067439	5.264087	0.283008	2.69	0.550455	224	12.49	11.1
2	lspm1403lspm3833_lc.fits	0.172983	5.266777	0.283326	8.21395	0.931646	442	14.319	13.2
2	lspm1405_lc.fits	0.267976	5.276198	0.582704	0.398692	0.897165	587	11.297	10.0
2	lspm1441_lc.fits	0.060994	5.431336	0.963376	2.99	0.517861	126	12.969	12.1
2	lspm1876_lc.fits	0.140267	1.448262	0.588299	0.997226	0.759187	1539	12.454	12.0
2	lspm1926_lc.fits	0.021373	1.846896	0.381167	19.32699	0.606368	90	11.803	11.2
2	lspm1926_lc.fits	0.056298	1.847412	0.38444	1.99	0.352325	58	12.509	11.6
2	lspm2304_lc.fits	0.04614	4.772002	0.452684	0.203543	0.70717	2679	12.681	12.3
2	lspm2359_lc.fits	0.229248	5.336967	0.543994	1.99	0.440903	1120	10.867	6.7
2	lspm2386_lc.fits	0.103227	5.606424	0.700169	7.06	0.978957	225	14.368	13.5
2	lspm2418_lc.fits	0.1022	5.93969	0.781832	28.318	0.568616	578	11.498	11.2
2	lspm2454_lc.fits	0.07204	6.241168	0.737704	0.134737	0.717748	1223	13.376	12.4
2	lspm2471_lc.fits	0.081761	0.073726	1.017765	5.21	0.371581	264	11.083	10.2
2	lspm2600_lc.fits	0.171591	0.483215	1.05684	1.99	0.68835	211	13.021	12.1
2	lspm2629_lc.fits	0.074803	0.591938	1.016558	0.203543	0.59242	263	13.788	13.0
2	lspm2670_lc.fits	0.089509	0.754889	1.00431	9.424871	0.478754	286	11.227	10.8
2	lspm2670_lc.fits	0.456995	0.745711	1.000977	0.997226	0.532091	205	14.772	14.1
2	lspm2675_lc.fits	0.064884	0.784167	1.339049	19.32699	0.614232	438	12.345	11.4
2	lspm2726_lc.fits	0.195949	0.909729	1.236674	1.67	0.897139	2079	14.758	14.1
2	lspm2770_lc.fits	0.106621	1.084203	1.384605	4.23	0.584855	128	13.967	13.4
2	lspm2789_lc.fits	0.03992	1.120255	1.481405	0.997226	0.741856	5167	12.738	12.3
2	lspm2827_lc.fits	0.163885	1.2658	1.241697	4.067234	0.812317	457	12.594	12.1
2	lspm2827_lc.fits	0.321819	1.254185	1.240206	2.996267	0.470513	274	13.826	13.0
2	lspm2827_lc.fits	0.181061	1.276239	1.240587	2.99	0.477623	381	14.117	13.7
2	lspm2883_lc.fits	0.04551	1.497277	0.78325	0.53	0.874914	243	13.417	13.0
2	lspm2918_lc.fits	0.04586	1.696714	0.305915	1.49	0.44656	68	13.603	12.7
2	lspm3547_lc.fits	0.199508	4.255627	0.017339	5.36	0.424628	185	14.74	14.5
2	lspm3605_lc.fits	0.169845	4.478308	0.556559	1.64	0.431389	335	13.376	13.0
2	lspm3612_lc.fits	0.157527	4.522309	1.214477	0.17	0.718573	274	12.391	12.0
2	lspm3624_lc.fits	0.016333	4.554698	0.077235	3.26	0.429774	73	9	8.5
2	lspm3624_lc.fits	0.073015	4.562095	0.075768	2.99	0.29765	46	13.866	13.1
2	lspm3645_lc.fits	0.158238	4.605748	0.240943	0.869101	0.540978	134	13.956	13.6
2	lspm3645_lc.fits	0.120693	4.610865	0.244225	2.99	0.343702	105	14.605	13.9
2	lspm3658_lc.fits	0.014113	4.684346	0.079732	3.05	0.713502	142	11.697	11.0
2	lspm3658_lc.fits	0.072432	4.68139	0.08196	2.99	0.783637	234	13.991	12.9
2	lspm3696_lc.fits	0.060901	4.830708	0.029763	1.99	0.516264	228	11.735	11.1
2	lspm3696_lc.fits	0.101212	4.824746	0.030835	1.9834	0.518503	200	12.517	11.8
2	lspm3696_lc.fits	0.143081	4.828935	0.030282	0.64	0.681721	200	13.348	12.5
2	lspm3712_lc.fits	0.06671	4.875546	0.355987	2.241289	0.624845	2061	12.498	12.2
2	lspm3712_lc.fits	0.058267	4.873536	0.361432	0.997226	0.934297	3490	13.703	13.2

2	lspm3765_lc.fits	0.081845	5.055646	0.325759	2.996267	0.90727	330	11.351	9.3
2	lspm3813_lc.fits	0.046582	5.212629	0.283787	10.17314	0.627343	300	12.956	12.0
2	lspm3816_lc.fits	0.163881	5.223087	0.383949	3.8	0.97765	1054	14.7	13.
2	lspm3840_lc.fits	0.07391	5.283544	0.113344	30.10276	0.430114	2223	11.969	11.1
2	lspm3846_lc.fits	0.061605	5.29413	0.018394	1.01258	0.443381	1374	11.115	10.
2	lspm3846_lc.fits	0.02423	5.293835	0.018153	4.87	0.732497	1373	12.158	11.5
2	lspm3848_lc.fits	0.10913	5.309436	0.104744	2.99	0.279535	78	12.663	11.9
2	lspm3852_lc.fits	0.142956	5.326336	0.626164	3.01	0.653472	482	10.382	7.6
2	lspm3863_lc.fits	0.472703	5.358654	0.59472	1.99	0.660868	783	10.127	7.0
2	lspm3868_lc.fits	0.136224	5.389263	0.140246	5	0.308994	64	13.569	13.2
2	lspm3881_lc.fits	0.145887	5.42433	0.084611	5.606009	0.627047	92	13.859	13.6
2	lspm3954_lc.fits	0.067388	5.657975	0.294149	5.3	0.339031	262	13.617	12.7
2	lspm3993_lc.fits	0.082376	5.797298	1.119799	7.76	0.969453	641	12.319	11.6
2	lspm3993_lc.fits	0.063244	5.797677	1.121787	3.16	0.726296	320	13.163	12.4
2	lspm4057_lc.fits	0.141672	6.046941	0.792646	0.132694	0.786323	507	14.777	14.
2	lspm4121_lc.fits	0.024045	6.255961	0.909693	2.99	0.637129	249	11.525	10.6
2	lspm1341_lc.fits	0.033767	5.075117	0.510928	1.95	0.639318	1149	10.741	9.5
2	lspm1341_lc.fits	0.093358	5.069643	0.516708	6.04	0.153032	1149	12.365	11.5
2	lspm2353_lc.fits	0.081296	5.232515	0.542463	1.01	0.853396	1151	10.826	8.
2	lspm2353_lc.fits	0.269314	5.236419	0.539007	2.01	0.426047	1150	11.284	9.2
2	lspm2353_lc.fits	0.419947	5.232213	0.539657	0.997226	0.957388	4296	13.897	13.4
2	lspm2854_lc.fits	0.110245	1.358158	0.473563	0.584165	0.628409	2542	14.563	13.7
2	lspm2976_lc.fits	0.10266	1.970441	1.401311	0.723501	0.911514	2283	12.694	12.0
2	lspm3892_lc.fits	0.022472	5.449723	0.588285	0.982104	0.42859	1058	10.471	9.4
2	lspm3892_lc.fits	0.02305	5.455386	0.58649	30.10276	0.995926	2116	11.498	11.4
2	lspm3892_lc.fits	0.082827	5.455688	0.58664	1.9834	0.692915	3169	13.355	13.0
2	lspm2912_lc.fits	0.034968	1.665613	1.15449	3.089245	0.791956	4698	13.986	13.3
2	lspm3636_lc.fits	0.035438	4.585746	0.477634	20.54509	0.646516	1531	13.611	12.9
2	lspm3651_lc.fits	0.084641	4.65986	0.500308	0.331899	0.916151	1418	13.966	13.1
2	lspm3651_lc.fits	0.199188	4.658771	0.501915	3.01	0.808399	1415	14.069	12.3
2	lspm1557_lc.fits	0.119964	5.867811	0.909419	2.996267	0.789329	2898	9.282	7.8
2	lspm1557_lc.fits	0.021539	5.872389	0.909106	1.11	0.303484	2896	10.537	10.2
2	lspm1557_lc.fits	0.049745	5.864706	0.905684	6.26	0.760006	5796	11.654	11.0
2	lspm1557_lc.fits	0.069039	5.87421	0.906976	6.84	0.128133	2896	12.965	12.2
2	lspm1557_lc.fits	0.153994	5.867588	0.905471	6.34	0.759616	2964	13.521	14.2
2	lspm1557_lc.fits	0.096246	5.866123	0.904002	0.997226	0.975774	11541	14.978	14.1
2	lspm1983_lc.fits	0.108378	2.342259	0.75862	0.411064	0.97264	2068	14.381	13.7
2	lspm3728_lc.fits	0.152991	4.911303	0.676176	8.089396	0.154415	1224	11.956	11.2
2	lspm3728_lc.fits	0.073032	4.907366	0.675039	0.745952	0.808816	1223	13.791	13.4
2	lspm3728_lc.fits	0.100427	4.911468	0.67569	0.386692	0.623932	1224	14.228	13.
2	lspm2902_lc.fits	0.19974	1.598109	1.060313	0.015866	0.664398	4	14.731	13.8
2	lspm2970_lc.fits	0.0455	1.931014	0.156517	0.022205	0.427	22	13.843	12.9
2	lspm2970_lc.fits	0.114444	1.929487	0.158087	0.024711	0.439201	22	14.95	13.9
3	lspm1249_lc.fits	0.167018	4.72712	0.654736	0.252092	0.923056	1468	13.404	12.7

3	lspm1249_lc.fits	0.129656	4.723614	0.6542	0.640253	0.727658	1468	14.469	14.0
3	lspm1757_lc.fits	0.063937	0.624554	0.797858	1.48	0.731769	1829	12.499	12.3
3	lspm1757_lc.fits	0.045385	0.623748	0.798533	1.03	0.804514	1829	13.54	13.2
3	lspm1823_lc.fits	0.208205	1.073619	0.527942	2.99	0.225205	456	12.701	12.1
3	lspm1823_lc.fits	0.214862	1.073552	0.529558	2.99	0.190206	453	13.621	13.1
3	lspm1881_lc.fits	0.023721	1.481587	0.912618	2.996267	0.41891	716	11.299	10.9
3	lspm1881_lc.fits	0.084754	1.481705	0.913003	2.996267	0.771402	715	12.805	14.8
3	lspm1902_lc.fits	0.113734	1.627057	0.583823	2.99	0.947129	321	13.939	13.4
3	lspm1909_lc.fits	0.032545	1.674327	0.797839	13.59997	0.650445	131	13.969	13.3
3	lspm2202_lc.fits	0.12535	3.863897	1.020577	0.584165	0.682157	1471	14.821	14.1
3	lspm2323_lc.fits	0.038376	4.936824	0.465138	3.8	0.59434	558	11.872	11.6
3	lspm2323_lc.fits	0.127799	4.934512	0.465595	2.99	0.624097	126	12.058	11.4
3	lspm2323_lc.fits	0.194229	4.933952	0.466782	2.99	0.21592	64	13.32	12.8
3	lspm2323_lc.fits	0.621308	4.934535	0.464683	1.99	0.559909	988	14.148	13.3
3	lspm2324_lc.fits	0.04743	4.942232	0.796949	16.08915	0.351572	77	11.884	11.1
3	lspm2324_lc.fits	0.078191	4.938319	0.798138	1.21	0.837855	154	14.274	14.2
3	lspm2383_lc.fits	0.03727	5.571784	0.397172	4.77	0.105032	53	13	12.1
3	lspm2394_lc.fits	0.023704	5.701195	0.812834	7	0.642779	364	10.641	9.3
3	lspm2412_lc.fits	0.177294	5.867666	1.038615	5.13	0.348627	541	11.754	10.4
3	lspm2428_lc.fits	0.085828	5.99921	1.187449	3.99	0.559441	68	12.47	11.9
3	lspm2505_lc.fits	0.030254	0.203886	0.998038	26.63905	0.462757	210	11.603	10.7
3	lspm2505_lc.fits	0.052025	0.19945	0.993585	0.169444	0.426948	210	12.927	12.4
3	lspm2581_lc.fits	0.103902	0.428125	0.911733	3.6	0.937495	189	14.994	14.
3	lspm2654_lc.fits	0.019144	0.661641	0.923756	1.254101	0.565612	1336	11.77	11.
3	lspm2654_lc.fits	0.036995	0.66255	0.923922	26.63905	0.190713	1336	12.633	12.0
3	lspm2654_lc.fits	0.064874	0.655409	0.920385	29.19674	0.994325	4007	13.561	13.0
3	lspm2661_lc.fits	0.089235	0.70352	0.951546	19.92673	0.285961	314	12.721	11.7
3	lspm2673_lc.fits	0.175224	0.762057	0.598208	14.90573	0.849182	251	14.465	14.0
3	lspm2699_lc.fits	0.108091	0.836097	0.757045	6.19	0.581008	147	12.449	12.1
3	lspm2712_lc.fits	0.057479	0.885847	1.233645	0.200457	0.727538	283	13.994	13.0
3	lspm2719_lc.fits	0.150015	0.913057	1.243166	2.99	0.379231	63	11.153	10.3
3	lspm2719_lc.fits	0.148123	0.911796	1.242316	2.99	0.801466	134	12.217	11.6
3	lspm2719_lc.fits	0.166071	0.913133	1.240791	2.99	0.385463	67	13.52	13.1
3	lspm2836_lc.fits	0.054052	1.290012	0.756633	2.05	0.747839	1700	11.463	11.1
3	lspm2836_lc.fits	0.042215	1.289296	0.753263	20.23355	0.564096	1700	12.392	11.5
3	lspm2841_lc.fits	0.125837	1.317294	0.263181	2.99	0.91853	375	13.817	13.0
3	lspm2853_lc.fits	0.072062	1.361341	1.227782	2.99	0.356531	140	11.696	11.2
3	lspm2853_lc.fits	0.072625	1.361292	1.228408	2.99	0.361816	140	12.145	11.
3	lspm2853_lc.fits	0.145154	1.350536	1.231361	1.09	0.475744	227	13.663	13.3
3	lspm2856_lc.fits	0.023608	1.359688	0.419546	7	0.580413	154	11.941	10.
3	lspm2938_lc.fits	0.027303	1.781345	0.090649	25.83729	0.299816	370	10.787	10.0
3	lspm2965_lc.fits	0.050615	1.897378	0.024481	2.27	0.426011	2708	12.771	12.4
3	lspm2980_lc.fits	0.162188	1.970949	0.049207	0.331899	0.515669	1062	14.979	14.
3	lspm3036_lc.fits	0.056655	2.203677	0.163045	2.99	0.220989	133	13.282	12.9

3	lspm3051_lc.fits	0.153972	2.270409	0.122904	1.438984	0.369187	727	12.337	11.9
3	lspm3598_lc.fits	0.132514	4.456837	0.123843	3.53	0.285978	107	13.083	12.7
3	lspm3598_lc.fits	0.088403	4.459643	0.127483	1.72	0.524357	107	14.66	14
3	lspm3626_lc.fits	0.859539	4.570251	0.359927	0.997226	0.775094	990	13.633	13.0
3	lspm3689_lc.fits	0.025256	4.78846	0.355793	0.152256	0.578882	266	12.881	12.4
3	lspm3689_lc.fits	0.049695	4.783473	0.35517	0.89	0.52916	424	13.055	12.5
3	lspm3704_lc.fits	0.059683	4.851755	0.359856	1.27341	0.68092	100	12.193	11.
3	lspm3704_lc.fits	0.044811	4.849934	0.354604	4.71	0.495004	100	13.448	12.6
3	lspm3728_lc.fits	0.115295	4.911303	0.676177	8.089396	0.407059	2060	11.956	11.2
3	lspm3750_lc.fits	0.123672	5.000664	0.416296	2.99	0.90806	128	11.839	10.8
3	lspm3751_lc.fits	0.412505	5.008646	0.081851	0.5	0.494181	768	10.711	8.3
3	lspm3751_lc.fits	0.339881	5.009572	0.084123	0.331899	0.802477	631	11.555	11.
3	lspm3761_lc.fits	0.082317	5.025423	0.692555	2.99	0.921944	128	14.779	14.4
3	lspm3794_lc.fits	0.098515	5.166856	0.709859	2.99	0.211832	72	11.531	11.4
3	lspm3794_lc.fits	0.098144	5.169413	0.71074	0.997226	0.693781	283	13.529	13.3
3	lspm3804_lc.fits	0.044006	5.197476	0.351668	2.01	0.62745	843	10.058	8.
3	lspm3811_lc.fits	0.101917	5.207328	0.309059	2.48	0.857528	227	11.086	10.4
3	lspm3822_lc.fits	0.118208	5.220106	1.13378	2.99	0.362001	349	12.668	12.3
3	lspm3822_lc.fits	0.125731	5.220089	1.133966	2.99	0.344362	349	13.136	12.7
3	lspm3857_lc.fits	0.13459	5.341899	0.043454	15.84518	0.666018	228	14.394	13.9
3	lspm3865_lc.fits	0.098037	5.359845	0.412984	2.99	0.926296	521	13.587	12.9
3	lspm3897_lc.fits	0.095832	5.476808	0.365086	0.331899	0.768987	894	13.605	13.2
3	lspm3920_lc.fits	0.041725	5.534242	0.953486	1.01258	0.736933	547	11.458	9.6
3	lspm3920_lc.fits	0.289429	5.540059	0.951063	0.952545	0.936506	1094	12.822	11.4
3	lspm3924_lc.fits	0.042808	5.525529	1.441136	2.32	0.487236	2274	12.66	11.9
3	lspm3969_lc.fits	0.152774	5.72204	0.816807	2.99	0.422552	132	11.589	11.1
3	lspm3974_lc.fits	0.07146	5.732674	0.778939	4.65	0.281581	205	12.358	11.4
3	lspm3974_lc.fits	0.118401	5.732914	0.781094	2.19	0.865069	412	13.561	13.0
3	lspm4006_lc.fits	0.127292	5.847999	1.035852	2.99	0.2152	138	11.585	10.4
3	lspm4006_lc.fits	0.064678	5.847477	1.034371	2.99	0.219366	138	12.815	11.8
3	lspm4006_lc.fits	0.108729	5.859685	1.033117	0.997226	0.787785	703	13.456	12.2
3	lspm4039_lc.fits	0.030306	5.983033	0.902727	0.203543	0.684823	1463	12.912	12.4
3	lspm463_lc.fits	0.103817	1.782687	0.650509	0.85	0.563987	158	12.53	12.2
3	lspm3625_lc.fits	0.126205	4.549964	1.214369	2.996267	0.435328	1791	14.614	13.9
3	lspm3884_lc.fits	0.013599	5.427335	0.268898	2.92	0.719111	973	11.874	10.9
3	lspm3884_lc.fits	0.055243	5.43213	0.264816	2.04	0.739876	974	13.213	12.8
3	lspm3884_lc.fits	0.083848	5.427137	0.263449	2.996267	0.834489	1797	14.339	13.8
3	lspm3908_lc.fits	0.027546	5.505606	0.696836	1.02	0.511101	1099	10.509	8.9
3	lspm3908_lc.fits	0.019153	5.509065	0.694789	23.57389	0.735877	1099	11.345	9.8
3	lspm3908_lc.fits	0.161782	5.506544	0.701099	0.23355	0.292389	1091	12.562	12.
3	lspm3908_lc.fits	0.169495	5.499767	0.694656	4.3	0.734777	4230	14.55	14.0
3	lspm4085_lc.fits	0.038903	6.13974	1.291716	2.996267	0.214199	2836	12.469	11.
3	lspm4085_lc.fits	0.058136	6.125509	1.288442	0.298232	0.941191	4337	13.913	13.4
3	lspm4085_lc.fits	0.14989	6.127012	1.293047	0.71253	0.930955	4338	14.775	14.2

3	lspm1835_lc.fits	0.116467	1.144653	0.452792	0.032041	0.337033	22	14.906	13.8
3	lspm1436_lc.fits	0.041369	5.412555	0.269844	1.076399	0.874562	1541	12.854	12.6
3	lspm1436_lc.fits	0.176214	5.409753	0.270458	0.145434	0.681008	1541	13.787	13.2
3	lspm3640_lc.fits	0.062465	4.591823	0.184197	0.392646	0.352502	2110	12.601	12.2
3	lspm3640_lc.fits	0.201977	4.590048	0.177646	5.99	0.637158	2111	13.145	12.8
3	lspm342_lc.fits	0.048084	1.277433	0.710779	0.352817	0.786661	1739	12.798	12.4
3	lspm2359_lc.fits	0.144555	5.336968	0.543993	2.996267	0.677643	2080	10.867	6.7
3	lspm3044_lc.fits	0.087472	2.240899	0.648674	3.02	0.135609	240	12.481	11.7
3	lspm2813_lc.fits	0.229562	1.222751	0.721658	28.75401	0.929243	944	13.937	13.3
5	lspm1296_lc.fits	0.272782	4.902484	0.242806	2.692335	0.812456	562	12.225	11.4
5	lspm1296_lc.fits	0.215758	4.901241	0.241523	4.11	0.698843	593	13.982	13.1
5	lspm1341_lc.fits	0.036424	5.075118	0.510928	1.95	0.65158	1171	10.741	9.5
5	lspm1411_lc.fits	0.131527	5.281152	0.283107	0.89	0.620631	226	10.738	10.4
5	lspm1411_lc.fits	0.186273	5.283448	0.284506	3.944821	0.583525	227	11.857	10.8
5	lspm1411_lc.fits	0.203706	5.287434	0.282821	0.620983	0.659483	227	13.554	13.2
5	lspm1417_lc.fits	0.107663	5.335523	0.187047	0.398692	0.653704	701	13.908	13.4
5	lspm1417_lc.fits	0.148006	5.333508	0.185161	0.230009	0.968319	2094	14.994	14.7
5	lspm1419_lc.fits	0.0797	5.347523	1.023703	6.07	0.332701	1425	11.562	10.7
5	lspm1419_lc.fits	0.065113	5.347837	1.025561	0.660121	0.820469	1425	12.977	12.5
5	lspm1419_lc.fits	0.155209	5.349762	1.025134	0.35	0.857707	1424	13.764	13.2
5	lspm1936_lc.fits	0.161632	1.911143	0.798727	1.216356	0.841217	10879	14.252	14.0
5	lspm2346_lc.fits	0.099134	5.139567	0.580331	1.01	0.468303	3217	9.233	7.8
5	lspm2346_lc.fits	0.079938	5.140204	0.579062	1.01	0.375252	3217	10.025	8.1
5	lspm2346_lc.fits	0.060407	5.144522	0.580325	1.9834	0.57379	3227	11.343	10.2
5	lspm2361_lc.fits	0.086318	5.384171	0.637194	2.98	0.580513	559	10.154	8.1
5	lspm2373_lc.fits	0.061937	5.506287	0.365065	8.731639	0.610407	227	12.644	11.7
5	lspm2403_lc.fits	0.087196	5.780031	1.180531	8.599236	0.685383	407	12.129	11.9
5	lspm2431_lc.fits	0.081684	6.068989	0.884351	0.64	0.734848	1151	11.447	11.0
5	lspm2431_lc.fits	0.129905	6.06792	0.882674	0.997226	0.717063	1025	12.439	11.6
5	lspm2431_lc.fits	0.268005	6.067937	0.88066	0.997226	0.776979	1045	14.655	14.2
5	lspm2555_lc.fits	0.081154	0.337238	1.136936	17.63391	0.444181	449	11.889	10.7
5	lspm2555_lc.fits	0.056184	0.334311	1.131724	17.10318	0.68649	449	12.555	11.4
5	lspm2557_lc.fits	0.018417	0.345359	0.958435	9.141208	0.370598	1226	11.982	11.3
5	lspm2557_lc.fits	0.036507	0.342539	0.960094	14.90573	0.60278	1225	13.584	12.7
5	lspm2564_lc.fits	0.132211	0.363555	0.941511	0.89607	0.920907	266	14.322	13.4
5	lspm2587_lc.fits	0.04045	0.449287	0.672192	0.043494	0.524231	70	12.95	12.5
5	lspm2597_lc.fits	0.029155	0.460898	1.066974	1.99	0.630542	303	11.103	10.6
5	lspm2605_lc.fits	0.090081	0.492235	0.77479	10.32978	0.480587	63	14.241	13.4
5	lspm2618_lc.fits	0.032609	0.554798	0.867994	6.334921	0.578801	68	12.239	11.3
5	lspm2618_lc.fits	0.087962	0.554273	0.869752	0.182896	0.541445	68	13.6	13.0
5	lspm2621_lc.fits	0.232913	0.569078	0.816042	1.109801	0.706234	140	13.493	13.0
5	lspm2621_lc.fits	0.126353	0.569981	0.812458	0.780942	0.562356	141	14.67	14.2
5	lspm2777_lc.fits	0.019647	1.100009	0.622867	30.56625	0.673651	842	12.865	11.8
5	lspm2820_lc.fits	0.215213	1.246993	0.758685	0.952545	0.389907	113	12.704	12.2

5	lspm2825_lc.fits	0.142906	1.263263	0.89919	0.417393	0.692943	1856	11.049	10.6
5	lspm2825_lc.fits	0.039012	1.261901	0.903534	1.01	0.651665	1857	12.708	11.0
5	lspm2913_lc.fits	0.024803	1.654414	0.359222	1.71	0.533079	132	11.201	11.0
5	lspm2919_lc.fits	0.080125	1.704952	0.170292	2.78	0.631887	233	10.421	9.7
5	lspm2919_lc.fits	0.290171	1.702723	0.168136	5.02	0.890979	458	13.451	12.9
5	lspm2930_lc.fits	0.023214	1.749178	0.463261	2.64	0.62201	82	12.445	11.7
5	lspm2934_lc.fits	0.099974	1.7684	0.722062	0.05	0.674945	520	13.778	13.5
5	lspm2946_lc.fits	1.35084	1.80608	0.553894	0.997226	0.690952	1623	14.431	14.2
5	lspm3064_lc.fits	0.100644	2.342535	0.21909	0.138918	0.617351	121	13.342	12.9
5	lspm3331_lc.fits	0.168471	3.364858	1.519995	0.39	0.642675	4906	14.639	14.2
5	lspm3584_lc.fits	0.048841	4.404662	1.363039	4.56	0.624627	250	13.372	12.5
5	lspm3643_lc.fits	0.247459	4.603545	0.464003	0.471664	0.34008	1276	14.707	14.4
5	lspm3647_lc.fits	0.046133	4.633561	0.171696	1.02	0.689531	989	13.4	12.6
5	lspm3661_lc.fits	0.161344	4.689446	0.569655	1.88	0.4519	224	12.803	12.5
5	lspm3688lspm1263_lc.fits	0.125381	4.786852	0.085969	1.99	0.506891	403	10.116	8.8
5	lspm3688lspm1263_lc.fits	0.072253	4.788096	0.083263	0.982104	0.714854	401	12.764	12.3
5	lspm3753_lc.fits	0.031921	5.00597	0.497919	0.191475	0.466467	251	11.011	9.8
5	lspm3753_lc.fits	0.087827	5.005741	0.499353	0.997226	0.869148	745	13.386	12.6
5	lspm3783lspm3780_lc.fits	0.058061	5.100938	1.20048	17.90542	0.430477	307	12.06	11.3
5	lspm3825_lc.fits	0.06734	5.246298	0.126978	0.411064	0.568728	219	13.83	13.3
5	lspm3844_lc.fits	0.078189	5.292592	0.25501	3.01	0.603604	376	10.778	9.6
5	lspm3877_lc.fits	0.028081	5.416885	0.864298	1.99	0.784901	1532	11.129	9.2
5	lspm3877_lc.fits	0.239124	5.412671	0.867211	0.997226	0.974596	4592	13.52	12.9
5	lspm3898_lc.fits	0.173481	5.485985	1.075592	0.5	0.896055	1202	12.638	12.0
5	lspm3937_lc.fits	0.22904	5.574504	1.119395	6.03	0.669913	145	13.346	11.5
5	lspm3937_lc.fits	0.118583	5.567775	1.115782	0.152256	0.603384	145	14.619	13.9
5	lspm3946_lc.fits	0.028136	5.617795	0.976476	2.013939	0.833019	2232	10.85	9.0
5	lspm3946_lc.fits	0.107184	5.623312	0.976918	2.47	0.435078	2236	11.416	10.9
5	lspm3951_lc.fits	0.120284	5.653007	0.946401	3.76	0.618941	108	11.576	11.0
5	lspm3951_lc.fits	0.07236	5.650365	0.951664	7.845927	0.273179	108	12.274	10.9
5	lspm4010_lc.fits	0.023611	5.861394	1.357854	0.997226	0.943354	2605	12.978	12.3
5	lspm4022_lc.fits	0.058692	5.911365	0.58545	3.71	0.605605	214	12.496	12.2
5	lspm4049_lc.fits	0.020552	6.013679	0.992591	1.953325	0.717514	539	10.445	8.8
5	lspm4054_lc.fits	0.073415	6.016934	1.331008	0.73464	0.749734	1479	12.876	12.5
5	lspm4105_lc.fits	0.220285	6.196483	1.043046	4.6	0.714117	263	14.232	13.7
5	lspm449_lc.fits	0.090034	1.727818	0.20168	5.63	0.33023	1137	11.626	11.4
5	lspm449_lc.fits	0.158504	1.732061	0.200505	0.27	0.785576	1133	12.474	12.0
5	lspm630_lc.fits	0.079599	2.393464	0.700127	0.11	0.47155	166	13.72	12.0
5	lspm2368_lc.fits	0.038428	5.431865	0.23915	0.404831	0.374639	615	13.518	13.2
5	lspm2487_lc.fits	0.105813	0.131226	1.356534	0.47	0.68057	1998	12.744	12.2
5	lspm2757_lc.fits	0.220278	1.020493	0.422276	0.997226	0.828252	1592	14.76	14.3
5	lspm2824_lc.fits	0.038754	1.262694	0.639696	24.30542	0.270742	2353	12.221	11.2
5	lspm2824_lc.fits	0.174402	1.256647	0.644942	0.244505	0.97963	2353	14.743	13.6
5	lspm3846_lc.fits	0.044688	5.29413	0.018394	0.982104	0.582451	675	11.115	10.0

5	lspm3846_lc.fits	0.039815	5.293835	0.018153	2.43	0.397943	675	12.158	11.5
5	lspm2679_lc.fits	0.064426	0.790024	1.095207	0.602293	0.702926	1724	13.488	12.9
5	lspm384_lc.fits	0.114861	1.433052	0.168637	0.110464	0.732079	1112	12.569	11.8
5	lspm3994_lc.fits	0.101133	5.804603	0.746745	0.81	0.60551	2580	13.997	13.6
5	lspm3994_lc.fits	0.134626	5.804243	0.751642	3.77	0.824719	5148	14.847	14.5
6	lspm1343_lc.fits	1.28765	5.066329	1.317421	0.997226	0.60172	2037	13.856	13.4
6	lspm1343_lc.fits	1.3013	5.066311	1.317762	0.997226	0.63502	1960	14.289	13.7
6	lspm1806_lc.fits	0.110147	0.953594	0.673805	1.235084	0.384772	236	12.46	12.0
6	lspm1831_lc.fits	0.117542	1.136463	0.739535	25.05965	0.785338	1855	12.811	12.1
6	lspm1831_lc.fits	0.054079	1.133985	0.739927	0.680605	0.506572	1854	13.592	13.0
6	lspm1977_lc.fits	0.127601	2.293186	0.319602	0.997226	0.476224	116	13.604	12.6
6	lspm1983_lc.fits	0.111988	2.342259	0.75862	0.411064	0.973861	2174	14.381	13.7
6	lspm2314_lc.fits	0.063422	4.881519	1.270643	1.506481	0.810784	1732	13.674	13.0
6	lspm2355_lc.fits	0.160616	5.255729	0.926111	0.42382	0.384869	4159	12.044	11.4
6	lspm2374_lc.fits	0.055312	5.509391	0.611464	1.85	0.724665	164	12.109	11.5
6	lspm2374_lc.fits	0.17909	5.508862	0.608981	0.869101	0.909903	327	14.864	14.3
6	lspm2424_lc.fits	0.915713	5.977412	0.792923	0.997226	0.62909	753	13.689	13.1
6	lspm2496_lc.fits	0.042549	0.159773	1.07617	1.235084	0.244358	72	10.725	10.4
6	lspm2496_lc.fits	0.092132	0.172183	1.081525	7.35	0.467842	142	12.281	12.1
6	lspm2502_lc.fits	0.111619	0.195514	0.810195	0.24	0.739922	291	12.879	12.4
6	lspm2509_lc.fits	0.163509	0.205642	1.053374	0.4	0.710875	313	12.571	12.2
6	lspm2578_lc.fits	0.047972	0.421231	0.723196	5.09	0.306358	256	12.662	12.0
6	lspm2580_lc.fits	0.110559	0.417097	0.782707	1.092972	0.597774	82	13.827	13.6
6	lspm2596_lc.fits	0.028927	0.457339	0.976362	0.99	0.582352	350	11.63	10.8
6	lspm2610_lc.fits	0.131593	0.50718	0.731575	6.89	0.361869	305	14.723	13.9
6	lspm2676_lc.fits	0.031948	0.772376	0.859284	5.72	0.338021	147	12.14	11.3
6	lspm2785_lc.fits	0.765494	1.120261	0.714566	0.997226	0.546596	326	13.435	12.5
6	lspm2818_lc.fits	0.176082	1.24022	1.128343	0.24827	0.366542	2194	14.562	14.1
6	lspm2851_lc.fits	0.099585	1.333685	0.919616	29.64629	0.990511	6013	15	14.1
6	lspm2899_lc.fits	0.108706	1.589606	0.532304	7.01	0.178106	514	10.114	8.9
6	lspm2899_lc.fits	0.497708	1.591062	0.529635	0.997226	0.788385	513	13.061	12.2
6	lspm2923_lc.fits	0.075057	1.730524	0.107489	5.15	0.479732	67	12.211	11.4
6	lspm2961_lc.fits	0.043317	1.884028	0.17998	13.39374	0.545654	72	12.819	12.1
6	lspm3001_lc.fits	0.212086	2.068062	0.927959	1.9834	0.428565	2432	13.01	12.7
6	lspm3011_lc.fits	0.229452	2.11399	0.146573	3.1	0.572239	121	14.456	13.5
6	lspm3637_lc.fits	0.063937	4.585864	0.315998	24.67966	0.319354	266	13.262	12.5
6	lspm3639_lc.fits	0.105238	4.590953	0.414636	0.89607	0.572447	5348	12.428	12.1
6	lspm3640_lc.fits	0.061645	4.591823	0.184197	0.244505	0.336804	2779	12.601	12.2
6	lspm3673_lc.fits	0.023803	4.732792	0.240295	2.99	0.608888	383	11	10.0
6	lspm3673_lc.fits	0.10329	4.732703	0.244344	0.216372	0.928429	769	12.254	11.9
6	lspm3729_lc.fits	0.285002	4.910457	0.12814	0.99	0.420137	105	10.746	9.0
6	lspm3729_lc.fits	0.265631	4.912622	0.129202	4.88574	0.60561	104	11.791	10.6
6	lspm3734_lc.fits	0.290945	4.930057	0.310779	3.97	0.681445	247	10.259	8.8
6	lspm3734_lc.fits	0.074593	4.935557	0.306102	24.30542	0.485411	242	12.201	11.9

6	lspm3763_lc.fits	0.035255	5.053439	0.499962	2.99	0.80791	1146	12.572	12.1
6	lspm3776_lc.fits	0.424657	5.088704	0.166783	0.5	0.523067	960	9.665	7.5
6	lspm3776_lc.fits	0.092562	5.086025	0.16622	1.01258	0.315789	960	10.028	8.3
6	lspm3776_lc.fits	0.067096	5.0842	0.171036	30.56625	0.993671	2879	11.944	10.1
6	lspm3776_lc.fits	0.133212	5.087721	0.171066	1.9834	0.991136	1918	12.982	11.8
6	lspm3847_lc.fits	0.144229	5.311327	0.690345	7.01	0.101147	115	10.219	9.0
6	lspm3869_lc.fits	0.079827	5.399992	1.112116	1.87	0.563256	2569	13.305	12.8
6	lspm3875_lc.fits	0.263397	5.404436	1.133042	0.997226	0.298294	140	14.387	13.8
6	lspm3884_lc.fits	0.097714	5.428376	0.265783	0.611566	0.805599	1143	14.989	14.6
6	lspm3889_lc.fits	0.157524	5.448927	0.212585	0.37	0.548203	211	12.851	12.3
6	lspm3890_lc.fits	0.147346	5.456413	1.019865	4.08	0.961128	242	12.918	12.3
6	lspm3890_lc.fits	0.070408	5.445032	1.020923	23.57389	0.644769	121	13.499	12.5
6	lspm3890_lc.fits	0.170594	5.4498	1.016324	0.411064	0.682044	122	14.182	13.6
6	lspm3908_lc.fits	0.030963	5.505606	0.696836	1.99	0.706427	1297	10.509	8.9
6	lspm3908_lc.fits	0.166123	5.506543	0.701099	0.23355	0.396355	1284	12.562	12.
6	lspm3918_lc.fits	0.09437	5.532362	0.349169	2.29	0.613255	430	12.459	12.2
6	lspm3944_lc.fits	0.079196	5.598292	1.181459	15.84518	0.528323	395	13.793	12.
6	lspm3973_lc.fits	0.144423	5.732419	0.395603	0.471664	0.468161	310	13.737	13.1
6	lspm3982_lc.fits	0.237178	5.745604	1.392869	0.997226	0.810141	3272	12.21	11.7
6	lspm3983_lc.fits	0.033848	5.773456	1.087226	1.99	0.544667	162	10.602	9.2
6	lspm3995_lc.fits	0.077584	5.814487	0.748645	0.997226	0.752383	284	14.998	14.0
6	lspm4040_lc.fits	0.061694	5.980448	1.078101	5.52	0.866809	378	12.655	11.7
6	lspm4066_lc.fits	0.099989	6.070441	0.961629	0.997226	0.730883	279	14.228	13.7
6	lspm432_lc.fits	0.05392	1.631686	0.899118	0.94	0.844497	4174	12.981	12.2
6	lspm432_lc.fits	0.159396	1.63022	0.905025	0.549531	0.858802	4174	13.516	12.7
6	lspm432_lc.fits	0.482358	1.626906	0.901436	2.996267	0.102976	3664	14.18	13.7
6	lspm531_lc.fits	0.04827	2.059869	0.098688	3.39	0.447822	2688	11.453	11.
6	lspm1279_lc.fits	0.264021	4.861003	0.388716	0.331899	0.871155	1014	14.382	13.9
6	lspm1710_lc.fits	0.168665	0.272074	0.9458	0.307487	0.617227	1677	13.522	12.9
6	lspm1947_lc.fits	0.120376	2.0121	0.311594	6.04	0.526755	1423	14.69	13.8
6	lspm3955_lc.fits	0.211064	5.664187	0.926701	6.7	0.092574	944	10.358	9.2
6	lspm3955_lc.fits	0.032621	5.660386	0.920629	0.97	0.859917	943	11.95	9.9
6	lspm3955_lc.fits	0.105326	5.661784	0.924031	3.45	0.812557	3777	13.568	12.3
6	lspm4097_lc.fits	0.803153	6.152128	1.209824	2.99	0.753519	1219	11.404	10.2
6	lspm4097_lc.fits	0.038702	6.159661	1.206315	0.99	0.692556	1359	12.891	12.2
6	lspm1190_lc.fits	0.238508	4.530764	0.201663	6.89	0.645471	2056	14.556	14.1
6	lspm2879_lc.fits	0.051698	1.489536	0.157587	5.74	0.376845	1304	12.524	11.4
6	lspm2512_lc.fits	0.24651	0.2153	1.082625	0.99	0.654958	970	11.171	6.8
6	lspm2512_lc.fits	0.151732	0.215957	1.082226	1.75	0.939979	1930	13.873	12.9
6	lspm2512_lc.fits	0.24642	0.213622	1.081996	2.99	0.714502	2850	14.808	12.7
6	lspm2317_lc.fits	0.036153	4.896292	0.548125	0.723501	0.760088	341	12.947	12.4
6	lspm2399_lc.fits	0.140869	5.728452	0.481378	0.015625	0.802975	18	14.662	13.9
6	lspm3804_lc.fits	0.025036	5.199405	0.35494	1.02	0.315253	555	11.002	10.2
6	lspm3911_lc.fits	0.062511	5.513506	0.302088	27.88859	0.263117	3320	13.394	12.6

6	lspm3911_lc.fits	0.089653	5.51131	0.300554	0.457468	0.596269	3320	14.693	14.1
6	lspm4042_lc.fits	0.172416	6.000215	1.309089	0.54	0.365748	139	12.45	11.
7	lspm1436_lc.fits	0.153352	5.409753	0.270457	0.41	0.828707	2782	13.787	13.2
7	lspm1496_lc.fits	0.158348	5.647617	0.031714	0.417393	0.664695	508	14.786	14.4
7	lspm1513_lc.fits	0.015396	5.707035	0.879971	4.61	0.588609	720	10.355	10.1
7	lspm1628_lc.fits	0.05976	6.135516	0.929961	7.15	0.181137	1593	11.896	11.1
7	lspm1628_lc.fits	0.420436	6.127787	0.926068	0.331899	0.779022	1590	13.641	13.2
7	lspm1628_lc.fits	0.1293	6.136342	0.926843	0.392646	0.47137	1593	14.452	14.0
7	lspm1675_lc.fits	0.026642	0.00449	0.835734	28.75401	0.499995	68	12.804	12.1
7	lspm1729_lc.fits	0.102823	0.485551	0.375421	0.289256	0.417704	1978	13.973	13.7
7	lspm1835_lc.fits	0.087115	1.144387	0.450643	0.6	0.69159	500	13.059	11.9
7	lspm2075_lc.fits	0.162387	2.97032	0.815356	2.99	0.200087	37	14.67	14.2
7	lspm2300_lc.fits	0.118605	4.689854	1.232745	2.99	0.441142	49	13.843	13.3
7	lspm2313_lc.fits	0.047698	4.889269	0.522654	2.99	0.240573	33	13.46	12.9
7	lspm2337_lc.fits	0.127975	5.060842	0.724874	0.36	0.94566	911	13.551	13.2
7	lspm2338_lc.fits	0.043278	5.063039	0.481505	3.32	0.240696	1622	12.374	11.7
7	lspm2343_lc.fits	0.140568	5.106339	0.629137	2.99	0.753946	137	13.685	13.3
7	lspm2347_lc.fits	0.098521	5.18222	0.62727	2.99	0.242476	362	10.893	10.1
7	lspm2347_lc.fits	0.135125	5.182403	0.626199	2.99	0.942991	678	12.187	11.8
7	lspm2352lspm3823_lc.fits	0.138629	5.221073	1.010688	2.99	0.205793	77	11.51	11.3
7	lspm2352lspm3823_lc.fits	0.097465	5.220649	1.010321	2.99	0.190979	77	12.339	11.9
7	lspm2352lspm3823_lc.fits	0.106321	5.220829	1.009982	2.99	0.18607	77	13.25	12.3
7	lspm2353_lc.fits	0.1842	5.239359	0.539439	6.97	0.107647	898	9.582	8.6
7	lspm2353_lc.fits	0.152006	5.236419	0.539007	27.04922	0.98763	1795	11.284	9.2
7	lspm2375_lc.fits	0.042443	5.510813	0.395271	23.21643	0.360785	63	12.83	12.1
7	lspm2429_lc.fits	0.201193	6.009728	1.078192	0.347467	0.755541	2624	13.766	12.4
7	lspm254_lc.fits	0.223659	0.890392	0.733893	4.99	0.928046	106	13.026	12.6
7	lspm2642_lc.fits	0.117709	0.630725	0.594093	0.5	0.485141	3442	14.907	13.9
7	lspm2657_lc.fits	0.104456	0.681952	1.243017	2.99	0.378907	62	12.468	11
7	lspm2657_lc.fits	0.078175	0.666217	1.245788	2.99	0.782471	133	13.429	12.4
7	lspm2780_lc.fits	0.152019	1.117723	0.692127	2.99	0.260648	180	13.486	12.4
7	lspm2780_lc.fits	0.155068	1.117968	0.692218	2.99	0.919547	360	14.885	13.7
7	lspm2819_lc.fits	0.195026	1.241403	0.263523	2.99	0.25354	56	12.103	11.2
7	lspm2819_lc.fits	0.191366	1.241503	0.263282	2.99	0.255783	56	13.115	12.
7	lspm2819_lc.fits	0.132742	1.241779	0.263189	2.99	0.326182	56	14.567	13.6
7	lspm2824_lc.fits	0.039418	1.262695	0.639696	24.30542	0.243322	2060	12.221	11.2
7	lspm2844_lc.fits	0.126981	1.327355	1.194947	2.99	0.207811	217	12.435	12.0
7	lspm2844_lc.fits	0.085754	1.328237	1.197562	2.99	0.411855	210	13.536	12.9
7	lspm2845_lc.fits	0.109703	1.326295	1.068445	2.99	0.950041	190	13.359	12.5
7	lspm2942_lc.fits	0.131024	1.796901	0.891003	2.99	0.318274	61	13.832	13.5
7	lspm2953_lc.fits	0.032391	1.851165	0.299284	0.302824	0.540459	103	11.963	11.5
7	lspm3144_lc.fits	0.079005	2.62659	1.416763	0.194424	0.475669	154	13.39	13.
7	lspm3193_lc.fits	0.129995	2.814055	0.118213	4.48	0.467669	127	13.182	12.9
7	lspm3316_lc.fits	0.306719	3.366481	0.421021	11.14989	0.456387	114	14.964	14.5

7	lspm3583_lc.fits	0.15544	4.403837	0.907282	2.99	0.272562	140	13.838	13.0
7	lspm3594_lc.fits	0.158414	4.434299	1.126596	2.99	0.237005	80	13.046	12.2
7	lspm3621_lc.fits	0.205027	4.550195	0.553202	2.99	0.241674	59	12.054	11.6
7	lspm3659_lc.fits	0.021396	4.689962	0.379817	6.334921	0.565309	95	12.883	12.5
7	lspm3659_lc.fits	0.173295	4.684917	0.381572	4.99	0.303953	49	14.77	14.0
7	lspm3695_lc.fits	0.098957	4.823641	0.530577	4.52	0.827966	102	14.532	14.2
7	lspm3744_lc.fits	0.041231	4.978218	0.718959	2.99	0.145156	46	12.366	12.1
7	lspm3744_lc.fits	0.185126	4.984407	0.71603	2.99	0.466198	112	13.467	13.0
7	lspm3749_lc.fits	0.157554	4.995761	1.115426	2.99	0.25374	90	12.235	11.1
7	lspm3749_lc.fits	0.129487	4.995821	1.114988	2.99	0.273215	90	14.303	14.0
7	lspm3775_lc.fits	0.085399	5.080533	0.07477	0.326867	0.838108	740	12.919	12.5
7	lspm3777_lc.fits	0.148946	5.077307	1.345193	2.99	0.345793	295	12.861	12.4
7	lspm3777_lc.fits	0.135387	5.076131	1.345614	2.99	0.513865	296	13.829	13.0
7	lspm3791_lc.fits	0.116164	5.157195	0.951053	2.99	0.232958	141	12.155	11.8
7	lspm3791_lc.fits	0.104294	5.157933	0.951207	2.99	0.872116	340	13.752	13.3
7	lspm3807_lc.fits	0.043992	5.206153	0.955083	0.630544	0.508452	112	13.457	13.0
7	lspm3859_lc.fits	0.167563	5.341509	0.951786	2.99	0.223948	109	10.906	10.2
7	lspm3859_lc.fits	0.075758	5.34093	0.950891	2.99	0.252425	126	11.571	10.8
7	lspm3902_lc.fits	0.139072	5.486964	0.793491	2.99	0.961919	328	11.976	11.0
7	lspm3955_lc.fits	0.191356	5.664186	0.926701	6.7	0.208592	1408	10.358	9.2
7	lspm3987_lc.fits	0.181357	5.777098	0.939019	2.99	0.2509	163	11.774	10.8
7	lspm3987_lc.fits	0.176709	5.77721	0.938524	2.99	0.835774	490	12.065	11.6
7	lspm4012_lc.fits	0.133292	5.885156	0.454733	0.997226	0.837098	200	14.57	13.1
7	lspm4014_lc.fits	0.095824	5.895463	0.074165	2.99	0.291737	66	13.035	12.1
7	lspm4033_lc.fits	0.045002	5.946507	0.800761	1.55	0.597896	150	12.135	11.6
7	lspm4033_lc.fits	0.161426	5.944517	0.800852	2.99	0.927597	249	13.849	12.9
7	lspm4033_lc.fits	0.150063	5.9477	0.797896	2.99	0.852009	475	14.73	14.1
7	lspm4045_lc.fits	0.175747	6.005227	1.21668	1.01	0.387831	1873	10.068	8.4
7	lspm4045_lc.fits	0.191035	5.991392	1.219897	0.493788	0.854962	1873	14.767	14.1
7	lspm4085_lc.fits	0.024699	6.127952	1.292352	2.996267	0.159591	4334	11.47	10.4
7	lspm4085_lc.fits	0.05836	6.125508	1.288442	0.524909	0.945109	4334	13.913	13.4
7	lspm47_lc.fits	0.185183	0.177667	0.963176	2.99	0.3247	72	12.567	12.1
7	lspm527_lc.fits	0.092252	2.035777	0.346826	17.10318	0.869453	1500	14.553	13.7
7	lspm693_lc.fits	0.124356	2.662985	1.20946	2.99	0.269672	65	13.67	12.9
7	lspm80_lc.fits	0.061328	0.280342	1.09149	0.680605	0.691249	184	10.629	10.1
7	lspm1944_lc.fits	0.169189	1.990479	0.587065	0.56	0.345079	1327	14.637	14.3
7	lspm2314_lc.fits	0.063678	4.881519	1.270644	1.506481	0.782691	1115	13.674	13.0
7	lspm3946_lc.fits	0.018848	5.617795	0.976476	32	0.870904	901	10.85	9.0
7	lspm3946_lc.fits	0.11381	5.623312	0.976918	2.47	0.336075	532	11.416	10.9
7	lspm3946_lc.fits	0.095802	5.610755	0.976385	2.996267	0.975825	2116	12.978	11.3
7	lspm3946_lc.fits	0.102902	5.613166	0.975962	2.996267	0.652144	1432	13.036	11.9
7	lspm3988_lc.fits	0.144976	5.78737	0.03982	0.141057	0.108109	1057	13.624	13.1
7	lspm2303_lc.fits	0.03091	4.747479	0.200681	1.626085	0.649689	646	12.485	11.8
7	lspm2401_lc.fits	0.109003	5.75498	1.073424	3.15	0.971522	1746	13.373	12.2

7	lspm2401_lc.fits	0.116263	5.760211	1.067015	0.85	0.958793	2684	14.289	13.2
7	lspm2851_lc.fits	0.046072	1.342335	0.920631	2.996267	0.1773	2214	12.582	12.1
7	lspm2851_lc.fits	0.054105	1.342651	0.920549	2.996267	0.230653	2213	13.971	13.5
7	lspm3277_lc.fits	0.156626	3.162706	1.325191	0.584165	0.963195	1329	14.509	13.9
7	lspm531_lc.fits	0.069036	2.062172	0.09679	0.997226	0.815097	1913	13.374	12.7
7	lspm3331_lc.fits	0.168663	3.364875	1.519995	0.39	0.637658	4148	14.639	14.2
7	lspm1891_lc.fits	0.104116	1.568491	0.371435	0.032535	0.493443	13	14.949	13.
7	lspm3635_lc.fits	0.092571	4.590443	0.615045	2.99	0.896844	1150	14.955	13.9
7	lspm1801_lc.fits	0.095871	0.935444	0.496162	0.197417	0.091878	23	13.691	13.0
7	lspm1339_lc.fits	0.084295	5.072679	0.121565	1.02	0.344434	1427	10.388	8.8
7	lspm1339_lc.fits	0.086585	5.068547	0.119822	0.98	0.392067	1427	11.163	9.4
7	lspm1339_lc.fits	0.471489	5.073942	0.124327	0.997226	0.620839	1350	14.057	13.5
7	lspm2323_lc.fits	0.037093	4.936824	0.465138	0.79	0.258674	298	11.872	11.6
7	lspm2323_lc.fits	0.057935	4.937136	0.465995	8.340421	0.153541	298	12.989	12.1
7	lspm2323_lc.fits	0.293709	4.942292	0.467028	18.18111	0.347747	295	13.633	13.2
7	lspm2323_lc.fits	0.073978	4.936692	0.468043	14.45711	0.355604	297	14.588	13.9
8	lspm1239_lc.fits	0.086509	4.693306	1.016067	0.380829	0.663154	1444	12.388	12.
8	lspm1279_lc.fits	0.458812	4.861099	0.390604	0.997226	0.790247	1157	12.983	12.
8	lspm1324_lc.fits	0.044791	5.013423	0.465674	7.11	0.589862	137	10.046	8.9
8	lspm1324_lc.fits	0.028675	5.008678	0.462158	0.8	0.841554	137	11.576	10.8
8	lspm1747_lc.fits	0.430917	0.573063	0.876112	1	0.790797	2570	13.355	12.4
8	lspm1747_lc.fits	0.14131	0.581237	0.878214	1.99	0.872665	2923	14.705	13.9
8	lspm1807_lc.fits	0.184508	0.954562	0.359278	0.723501	0.925816	2436	14.611	14.0
8	lspm1883_lc.fits	0.109625	1.479494	0.705804	0.997226	0.923892	2208	13.768	13.5
8	lspm1904_lc.fits	0.123135	1.64695	0.764303	0.997226	0.903655	445	13.023	12.7
8	lspm1939_lc.fits	0.056758	1.967399	0.720269	2.99	0.440613	116	13.899	13.5
8	lspm1944_lc.fits	0.11153	1.993241	0.582348	1.333141	0.262347	1841	13.023	12.7
8	lspm1944_lc.fits	0.163241	1.990479	0.587064	0.56	0.438836	1843	14.637	14.3
8	lspm1949_lc.fits	0.106386	2.037597	1.331236	2.15	0.158065	14346	12.934	12.
8	lspm199_lc.fits	0.172399	0.719899	0.78538	0.177392	0.5587	936	13.758	13.2
8	lspm2267_lc.fits	0.128758	4.439006	0.234507	4.82	0.526179	222	14.591	14.3
8	lspm2294_lc.fits	0.077753	4.677551	0.260374	2.906088	0.337869	376	11.44	10.
8	lspm2303_lc.fits	0.036028	4.74748	0.200681	1.626085	0.628115	1050	12.485	11.8
8	lspm2316_lc.fits	0.086456	4.898171	0.42634	26.23511	0.958564	2810	13.948	13.1
8	lspm2319_lc.fits	0.051796	4.912177	0.303258	0.5	0.693418	252	10.873	9.4
8	lspm2368_lc.fits	1.20387	5.426212	0.239773	0.997226	0.617899	564	12.143	11.4
8	lspm2368_lc.fits	0.908496	5.425965	0.237212	0.997226	0.793606	693	13.817	13.3
8	lspm2368_lc.fits	0.854113	5.426206	0.238764	0.997226	0.666662	445	14.981	14.1
8	lspm2399_lc.fits	0.047616	5.721651	0.479138	2.99	0.419435	117	13.773	13.1
8	lspm2401_lc.fits	0.052105	5.746354	1.069492	2.99	0.376361	2383	12.997	12.
8	lspm2512_lc.fits	0.193744	0.215302	1.082624	2.01	0.601849	774	11.171	6.8
8	lspm2536_lc.fits	0.068242	0.273969	1.246352	5.88	0.636633	146	13.828	13.3
8	lspm2556_lc.fits	0.016051	0.353019	1.046496	14.23789	0.650372	204	11.154	10.
8	lspm2556_lc.fits	0.029939	0.3531	1.047946	6.5	0.528759	204	12.584	12.3

8	lspm2598_lc.fits	0.021942	0.470916	1.049373	2.99	0.263795	123	10.01	9.1
8	lspm2679_lc.fits	0.064309	0.790024	1.095207	0.602293	0.697185	1332	13.488	12.9
8	lspm2837_lc.fits	0.095091	1.294593	0.585567	0.289256	0.537111	301	11.479	10.8
8	lspm2837_lc.fits	0.064007	1.295958	0.587154	6.18	0.330854	301	13.274	12.2
8	lspm2861_lc.fits	0.181946	1.378925	0.990273	0.91	0.744491	2056	14.502	13.
8	lspm2866_lc.fits	0.101823	1.443117	0.525593	1.53	0.515552	112	14.885	14.1
8	lspm2884_lc.fits	0.114142	1.496697	0.714719	1.577144	0.688609	314	11.638	10.9
8	lspm2905_lc.fits	0.168331	1.612053	0.859221	0.723501	0.495172	115	14.783	14.4
8	lspm2963_lc.fits	0.13301	1.889916	0.64623	2.99	0.903371	2092	12.809	12.4
8	lspm2982_lc.fits	0.050434	1.982861	0.76548	2.99	0.386473	85	13.625	12.8
8	lspm3180_lc.fits	0.139303	2.730815	0.090686	0.51695	0.43185	679	14.375	13.9
8	lspm3501_lc.fits	0.093866	4.074102	1.129307	3.35	0.234265	432	13.74	13
8	lspm3633_lc.fits	0.09937	4.57912	0.589801	2.99	0.262669	172	13.197	12.6
8	lspm3657_lc.fits	0.97758	4.686625	0.140052	0.997226	0.376529	1151	12.217	11.7
8	lspm3662_lc.fits	0.061929	4.694936	0.330882	0.982104	0.633983	160	13.793	13.1
8	lspm3670_lc.fits	0.102047	4.728429	0.219058	3.01	0.836838	693	13.971	13.5
8	lspm3690_lc.fits	0.213363	4.78139	0.011721	14.02199	0.842858	228	14.988	14.3
8	lspm3701_lc.fits	0.022704	4.84744	0.221373	2.996267	0.635674	145	11.728	10.
8	lspm3701_lc.fits	0.137499	4.846724	0.2226	1.41	0.964336	434	14.93	14.0
8	lspm3708_lc.fits	0.028117	4.870008	0.245636	0.997226	0.781886	191	12.753	12.2
8	lspm3716_lc.fits	0.204207	4.884794	0.290326	0.99	0.582996	87	10.403	9.0
8	lspm3774_lc.fits	0.07318	5.08321	0.410853	0.630544	0.952497	3815	11.924	11.3
8	lspm3774_lc.fits	0.37549	5.085536	0.412377	27.4657	0.990723	12287	13.469	13.
8	lspm3782_lc.fits	0.129423	5.11028	0.49977	6.83787	0.317129	90	9.249	7.
8	lspm3782_lc.fits	0.046487	5.108281	0.502459	3.38	0.634656	192	10.757	9.3
8	lspm3782_lc.fits	0.045405	5.104319	0.502016	0.780942	0.990517	576	11.169	9.8
8	lspm3812_lc.fits	0.094437	5.213696	0.318242	3.54	0.322979	72	10.169	10.1
8	lspm3928_lc.fits	0.100261	5.563411	0.745812	1.676545	0.662426	240	11.782	11.2
8	lspm3938_lc.fits	0.031221	5.573268	0.937105	2.99	0.477149	49	11.81	10.5
8	lspm3988_lc.fits	0.272958	5.784603	0.042011	0.997226	0.669167	1425	13.997	13.5
8	lspm4027_lc.fits	0.075911	5.926716	0.868812	2.27	0.177728	71	11.16	10.4
8	lspm4079_lc.fits	0.16967	6.117092	0.76219	29.19674	0.975775	1182	14.569	14.0
8	lspm569_lc.fits	0.06122	2.221221	0.352376	2.99	0.327081	259	12.164	11.4
8	lspm2818_lc.fits	0.169691	1.240219	1.128343	0.24827	0.328932	2146	14.562	14.1
8	lspm3776_lc.fits	0.35636	5.088705	0.166783	0.99	0.372097	931	9.665	7.5
8	lspm3776_lc.fits	0.101724	5.086025	0.16622	1.01258	0.251503	931	10.028	8.3
8	lspm3776_lc.fits	0.067145	5.0842	0.171036	30.56625	0.990449	1862	11.944	10.1
8	lspm3776_lc.fits	0.145778	5.083604	0.170091	27.04922	0.993707	8303	13.831	13.2
8	lspm3831_lc.fits	0.08341	5.257344	0.665402	1.59	0.969052	2299	11.759	11.5
8	lspm3831_lc.fits	0.188396	5.256293	0.670006	30.10276	0.990792	5663	14.971	14.5
8	lspm3877_lc.fits	0.025769	5.416885	0.864298	1.99	0.707873	1485	11.129	9.2
8	lspm3877_lc.fits	0.165855	5.42123	0.86644	27.88859	0.832871	2971	13.059	11.6
8	lspm2454_lc.fits	0.069306	6.241168	0.737705	0.134737	0.68161	1196	13.376	12.4
8	lspm2454_lc.fits	0.083196	6.247422	0.736301	32	0.749618	1197	14.951	14.1

8	lspm3648_lc.fits	0.175167	4.633899	1.316207	0.12107	0.483304	174	13.642	12.9
8	lspm1249_lc.fits	0.155616	4.72712	0.654736	0.430345	0.860028	1158	13.404	12.7
8	lspm2913_lc.fits	0.345665	1.654332	0.355253	0.028791	0.417835	22	12.523	12.
8	lspm1628_lc.fits	0.027923	6.139111	0.928493	0.331899	0.808662	1419	12.657	12.0
8	lspm1628_lc.fits	0.116826	6.136342	0.926843	0.392646	0.174996	1417	14.452	14.0
8	lspm1838_lc.fits	0.029502	1.174309	1.040783	0.69	0.40764	1077	11.791	11.4
8	lspm1838_lc.fits	0.161535	1.162969	1.043151	0.493788	0.546503	1074	14.085	13.